

Gravitation at the Planck Scale

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July 14, 2024

Abstract

I present some equations for the treatment of infinitesimal gravitational fluctuations.

1 Introduction

The quantum action of gravity is given by:

$$G_{\hbar} = \int_{\mathcal{M}} \partial \left(\frac{((2^{n-k} + 2^{n-(k-1)})\hbar m)/G}{(16 - 4k)\pi^2} \right) \quad (1.1)$$

which generalizes to:

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} \partial \left(\frac{((p^{n-k} + p^{n-(k-p/2)})\hbar m)/G}{-\sqrt{2p}(-p^2 + k)\pi} \right) \quad (1.2)$$

as $k \rightarrow 0$, we have:

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} \partial \left(\frac{2^{n+1}\hbar m}{8\pi G} \right) + \partial \left(\frac{2^n \hbar m}{8\pi G} \right) \quad (1.3)$$

where

$$m = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} m_i - \Delta_i(m_{i-1})}{i} \cdot \frac{3}{4}\pi r^3 \cdot (m_i - m_{i-1})^{-2} \quad (1.4)$$

is the specific massive contribution of a spherical body with i marked points. The body's barycenter is given by integrating over all of the jets emanating from the sphere's origin:

$$\bar{B} = \iiint \left(\left(\frac{\partial(T_{xy} - \partial T_{xz})}{\partial T_{y'z'}} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial(T_{yz} - \partial T_{zx})}{\partial T_{x'y'}} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial(T_{zx} - \partial T_{xy})}{\partial T_{x'z'}} \right) \right) \quad (1.5)$$

with

$$x = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}}^{\infty} x_p \quad y = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}}^{\infty} y_p \quad z = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}}^{\infty} z_p \quad (1.6)$$

$$x' = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}+\sqrt{-1}}^{\infty+\sqrt{-\infty}} x_p \quad y' = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}+\sqrt{-1}}^{\infty+\sqrt{-\infty}} y_p \quad z' = \sum_{p=v_{\mathbb{E}}+\sqrt{-1}}^{\infty+\sqrt{-\infty}} z_p \quad (1.7)$$

The gravitational fluctuations of a system of resting bodies is given by:

$$\bar{B}\mathcal{F} = \bar{B} \otimes \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} g_j^i = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_i^j \otimes \bar{B} \quad (1.8)$$

where

$$g = \iint_{\mathbb{C}} \frac{\partial g_j}{\partial g_i} \quad i = j - k \quad \& \quad k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1.9)$$

We have

$$\lim_{0 \leftarrow k} g \cong \widetilde{Id}_B \quad (1.10)$$

so that for vanishing k , g gives the pseudo-identity on a body; in other words, for a system of bodies $\{B_0, B_1, \dots, B_N\}$, we have $B_N = B_{N-M}$ for all $M \leq N$. As in my previous works I have tried to express, the quasi-identity $\widetilde{Id}_\alpha$ on some object α is the identity obtained by lowering the dimensionality of said system under some map $\mathcal{S}_\alpha \mapsto \mathcal{S}'_\alpha$, thereby yielding a slice of the original system in which all intersecting points are identified with one another.

The upshot of pseudo-identities comes in two natural paths: firstly, the pursuit of a quasi-quantum description of nature, in which collectively excited virtual particles can be realized under a pre-specified transformation of the potential proper to the well in which they reside. Secondly, holographic ideas can be seamlessly integrated using pseudo-identities; if we have a Cartesian line $\gamma \cong [-.5, .5]$, we can describe the fibres tangent to the neighborhoods $\mathcal{U}(\mp .5)$ by working instead with representative points.

In terms of gravitation, these representatives are the barycentric points which I have described herein. In the ideal situation, these barycenters are perfect centroids, and so the geometric mean of a space coincides with the mean of gravitational forces exerted by the space. That is to say, the locus of curvature coincides with $\bar{B}$:

$$\sum_{r=0}^N \frac{\Delta_r B}{N} = \bar{B} \quad (1.11)$$

where $\Delta_r B = d(B, o)$ with o the origin; we then call r the “radius,” and a vector of length r is a “radial line,” or a ray.

It is typical that a physicist will choose only to work with geodesics in order to minimize the number of conundrums faced during their calculations; however, these geodesics are allowed to have a non-zero curvature, and the number $Curv(\gamma)$ of the geodesic partially defines the boundary conditions of a well containing mediator particles of the same type as γ .

2 Curvature of geodesics and transport

On a locally flat section of a Euclidean manifold, the transport of a particle ψ is given by:

$$T_\psi = \nabla_x^y p^{-1} d(\psi, \ell) \quad (2.1)$$

where x and y are antipodal points of the geodesic connecting ψ to the locus of curvature ℓ . On a curved space, this generalizes as:

$$\tilde{T}_\psi = \left(\nabla_x^y p^{-1} d(\psi, \ell) \right) \cdot \left(\left(\frac{1}{2} p \right) + Curv(\gamma) + \varepsilon^{n-k} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

where $Curv(\gamma)$ is normalized to the interval $[-1, 1 - \varepsilon]$.

2.1 Gravitational field strength

Let $\Gamma_x^y(\mathcal{G})$ denote the gravitational field strength in the interval $[x, y]$.

$$\Gamma_x^y(\mathcal{G}) = \int_x^y \hbar \times \left(\frac{dm}{dv} \cdot \lambda_{\mu\nu} \lambda^{\mu\nu} \cdot \exp(\tilde{T}_\psi) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

Notice that if we collapse the interval to a point, we have:

$$\Gamma_{x_0}^{x_1}(\mathcal{G}) = \int_x \hbar \times \left(\frac{0}{\infty} \cdot \lambda_{\mu\nu} \lambda^{\mu\nu} \cdot 1 \right) \quad (2.4)$$

We modify this equation accordingly:

$$\Gamma_x(\mathcal{G}) = \int_x \hbar \times \left(\frac{v_{\mathbb{E}} + \varepsilon^{n-k}}{\infty} \star \lambda_{\mu\nu} \lambda^{\mu\nu} \star c^p \right) \quad (2.5)$$

which gives us

$$\Gamma_x(\mathcal{G}) = \int_x \hbar \times \left(\varepsilon \star \Lambda \right)^p \quad (2.6)$$

For a point-particle ψ_0 , we have $\psi_0 \cong \mathbb{S}^0$, which decomposes into two parts:

$$\mathbb{S}^0 = \mathbb{S}^m \oplus \mathbb{S}^{-m} \quad (2.7)$$

consisting of positive (classical) dimensions and negative (internal) ones. The number m is given by subtracting the exhausted components (k -components) from the overall degrees of freedom n . The values $\pm m$ are known as the conjugate pre-dimensions of the particle, and they are first rank tensors.

Property 2.1. *Let $\Gamma_x^y(\mathcal{G}_{\psi_0}) = \alpha$ and $\Gamma_u^v(\mathcal{G}_{\psi'_0}) = \beta$. Then, we are free to concatenate by writing*

$$\alpha \circ \beta = \Gamma_{u-x}^{v+y}(\mathcal{G}_{\psi''_0}) = \vartheta \quad (2.8)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbb{I}_a = [x, y]$ and $\mathbb{I}_b = [u, v]$. Then, we are free to construct neighborhoods $\mathcal{U}(\psi_0) \cong \mathbb{I}_a$ and $\mathcal{U}(\psi'_0) \cong \mathbb{I}_b$. Then we take $\inf(\sup(\mathcal{U}([\psi_0]))) - \inf(\inf(\mathcal{U}([\psi_0])))$ and map it to $u - x$. Next, we take $\sup(\inf(\mathcal{U}([\psi_0]))) + \sup(\sup(\mathcal{U}([\psi_0])))$ and send it to $v + y$. This gives us a new interval $\mathbb{I}_c = [u - x, v + y]$.

We are then free to apply an arbitrary creation map $Cr_{\psi''_0} : \{\} \mapsto \mathbb{I}_c$, thereby instantiating the new point particle in this interval. $\square$

The above property gives rise to what I'd like to call ϑ -duality; specifically, it tells us that, given two spans of gravitational energy, there is always some third span which is a union of the two, given by the unique geodesic ϑ . If we were to take this idea literally, it says that for any concatenation of point particles (say, gravitons), there is a decay mode involving the whole system of particles, from which a unique travelling body apparently arises. This appearance is given by a spontaneous breaking of the system's gravitational symmetries; however, this phenomenon depends on one's choice of gauge.